

Nutritional Composition of *Carica papaya* (Papaya) Seeds from Bida, Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Despite the widespread consumption of papaya (*Carica papaya*) seeds for therapeutic purposes, limited research exists on their nutritional and anti-nutritional composition. This study evaluated the nutritional profile and anti-nutrient content of papaya seeds sourced from Bida, Niger State, Nigeria, focusing on their potential health benefits and safety. The AOAC recommendations were followed in the analysis of the proximate composition. AAS method was used to determine mineral content while the Phytate and oxalate were analysed using spectroscopic and titrimetric methods, respectively. Proximate analysis revealed a high carbohydrate (20.93% DW) and fibre (28.48% DW) content, indicating their role as an energy source and in cholesterol management. The seeds also contained residual moisture (5.35% DW) and ash (6.74% DW), suggesting low inorganic mineral levels. Elemental analysis identified magnesium (64.0 mg/kg) and calcium (658 mg/kg) as key minerals. Anti-nutrient assessment detected phytate (3.12 mg/100g), oxalate (7.50 mg/100g), hydrogen cyanide (0.25 mg/100g), tannins (0.1195 mg/100g), flavonoids (6.98 mg/100g), and steroids (1.08 mg/100g) at safe levels, while alkaloids (1.85 mg/100g) warranted caution. Findings suggest that papaya seeds are a nutrient-rich dietary component with therapeutic potential, though moderate consumption is advised due to alkaloid content. This study provides valuable insights for their safe utilization in food and traditional medicine.

Keywords: Anti-nutrients, *Carica papaya* seeds, Nutritional composition and Pawpaw

1.0 Introduction

The papaya (*Carica papaya* L.), also known as pawpaw, is a tropical fruit. While the fruit is widely studied, its seeds, rich in bioactive compounds, remain under investigated despite their traditional use in treating infections, digestive disorders, and as a contraceptive [1,2]. Recent studies highlight their antibacterial and anti-helminthic effects [3], yet gaps persist in understanding their nutritional and anti-nutritional composition. This study addresses these gaps by analyzing seeds from Bida, Nigeria, to elucidate their dietary and therapeutic potential. In addition to having antibacterial activity against *Trichomonas vaginalis* trophozoites, it may be used

cautiously to prevent toxicity in urogenital disorders such as trichomoniasis [4]. According to Krishna et al. [5], papaya seed macerate has a clinical potential on conjugal R plasmid transfer from *Salmonella typhimurium* to *Escherichia coli* in vitro and in the digestive tract of genotobiotic mice. The seeds, regardless of their fruit maturity stages, are reported to have bacteriostatic activity on gram positive and negative organisms which could be helpful in treating chronic skin ulcers [6].

According to Saba and Pattan [7], papaya seeds can yield between 30% and 34% oil with nutritional and functional qualities that are quite similar to those of olive oil. They also include 22% fibre, which helps

to relieve constipation and other digestive issues [8]. The seeds are utilized as food ingredients because they are edible when dried or fermented [9]. Daily papaya seed feeding (1–2% of meals) decreased the number of *helminths* in pullets' digestive tracts [10]. This implies that papaya seeds have nutritional benefits in addition to its function in illness treatment. Nevertheless, despite the seeds' many health benefits, little is known about their nutritional and anti-nutritional makeup. Thus, the purpose of this study is to assess the nutritional makeup of papaya seeds [11].

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

The fruit of the *carica papaya* was procured from the *Etsuko* Garden located in the Bida Local Government Area of Niger State, Nigeria. A porcelain pestle and mortar were used to grind the seed sample to a fine powder after it had been air dried for two weeks in the shade. Prior to analysis, the powder was kept in the Federal University Birnin Kebbi Chemistry Lab in an airtight container. The reagents used were obtained from Guangdong Guanghua Chemical Factory Co., Ltd. and included hexane (99.64%), sulphuric acid (99.55%), perchloric acid (99.70%), sodium hydroxide (99.46%), and other standard laboratory instruments.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Proximate Composition

The nutritional makeup of the papaya seed was estimated using the methodology outlined by standard method of AOAC [12] which was described by other scientists. The percentage weight method developed by Yerima and Kanawa [13] was used to determine the amount of accessible carbohydrates in the seed. It is achieved by subtracting the total percentages of crude protein, crude fat, crude fibre, ash content, and residual moisture from the sample, as indicated in equation 1.

$$\text{Available Carbohydrate} = 100 - [\% \text{protein} + \% \text{ash} + \% \text{fibre} + \% \text{crude lipid}] \dots \dots \dots 1$$

2.2.2 Anti-nutrients Determination

The phytate and oxalate were assessed by spectroscopic and titrimetric assays, respectively, as

Aliyu *et al.* [11] stated. A method outlined by Ezeonu and Ejikeme [14] was utilised to determine the alkaloid content. The content of hydrogen cyanide was measured as described in Pereira *et al.* [15]. Using Nwosu *et al.* [16] the concentration of steroids was measured. The method outlined by Michael *et al.* [17] was used to determine the tannin concentration. To determine the flavonoid contents, the Ayele *et al.* [18] method was employed.

3.0 Result and Discussion

3.1 Proximate composition of the papaya seeds

The result of proximate analysis (% DW) is presented on Table 1. The parameters analysed include; residual moisture (5.35%), ash (6.74%), crude lipid (26.69%), crude protein (11.81), crude fibre (28.48) and carbohydrate (20.93%) contents of *carica papaya* seeds.

Table 1: Proximate Composition of *Carica papayaseeds*

Parameter	Nutrient(%DW)
Residual Moisture	5.35 ± 0.27
Ash	6.74 ± 0.24
Crude Lipid	26.69 ± 0.91
Crude Protein	11.81 ± 0.14
Crude Fibre	28.48 ± 0.67
Available Carbohydrate	20.93 ± 0.67

Data are mean ± standard deviation of the triple result

The residual moisture content of the seeds in this study was 5.35 %, which is comparable to 5.00% reported by Oyeleke *et al.* [19]. However, Kolu et al. [20] reported lower level (3.50%) in the plant seeds. Low moisture content was reported to boost seed shelf life [21]. Wurochekkeet *et al.* [22] claimed a converse relationship between moisture content and ash content, while Alam *et al.* [23] stated a converse association between moisture content and energy [24]. According to Petkova and Antova, [25] the moisture content in this study is within the range of 4.27 to 5.63%, which suggests that it may contain a significant number of minerals and energy.

The sample's ash content was found to be 6.74% of the seed's mass, which is higher than the ash content of castor seeds (5.71%) [26] and lower than the 15.02% and 8-9% reported by Kolu et al. [20] and Oyeleke *et al.* [19] respectively. The amount of

ash in seeds is a sign of their mineral content. As per Ogunbode and Raji [24], seeds with an ash percentage of 8.1-19.2% are deemed to have low ash content, indicating a low amount of inorganic minerals in the sample. Therefore, in order to prevent their shortage, additional diets high in minerals are required [25].

The mean crude lipid content of the seed (26.69%) is marginally lower than the 28.30% reported by Rahmasariet *al.* [26], but it is equivalent to the range (18.30–27%) of percentage crude lipids extracted in seeds collected from various parts of the world [27]. Papaya seeds are considered an edible oil source due to their crude lipid production (18.3 to 27.0%) [28].

The seed's crude protein content is 11.81% of its dry weight, which is higher than the 9.65% reported by Kanadiet *al.* [28] and lower than the amount detected in the seed coat as reported by Afolabi and Ofobruketa [29]. But according to Koul *et al.* [30], papaya seeds do not contain any protein. Non-protein nitrogenous substances including alkaloids and isothiocyanates are said to be present in papaya protein, and the analytical method employed to ascertain the seed's total crude protein content may be the cause of the difference in crude protein content. Researchers may use a number of conversion variables, and their availability could also affect the overall crude protein levels [31].

Papaya seeds' crude fibre percentage (28.48%) was greater (21.25%) than that of Kanadiet *al.* [28] and lower (32–38%) than Vinhaet *al.* [31]. According to Martial-Didier *et al.* [32], foods with a 6% fibre content are classified as high in fibre. Therefore, the seed's high fibre content can be used to lower cholesterol and lessen the absorption of fat [33].

The papaya seeds have a comparable amount of carbohydrates (20.93%) as Moses and Olanrewaju's [33] study (19.71%). These seeds are a source of carbohydrates, according to Moses and Olanrewaju [33].

3.2 Mineral and Antinutrient composition of the papaya seeds

Table 2 displays the results of the minerals and antinutritional factors in papaya seeds. Calcium was the most abundant element, followed by potassium, while sodium was not detected. The result of anti-nutritional analysis show oxalate has the highest

concentration (7.52 mg/100 g) and hydrogen cyanide had the least (0.25mg/100 g).

Table 2: The Minerals and Anti-Nutritional Content of *Carica papayaseeds*

Element	Concentration
Ca(mg/100g)	65.80 ±1.54
Mg(mg/100g)	6.40±0.73
Na(mg/100g)	BDL
K(mg/100g)	9.55±0.87
Zn(mg/100g)	1.35±2.27
Flavonoid (g/100g)	6.98±2.09
Alkaloid(g/100g)	1.85±0.03
Phytate(g/100g)	3.12±0.01
Oxalate(g/100g)	7.52±0.06
HCN (g/100g)	0.25±0.47
Tannin(g/100g)	0.12 ±0.02
Steroid(g/100g)	1.08±0.07

Data are mean ± standard deviation of the triple result

The estimated calcium content of the seed was 658 mg/kg, which is more than the Enemoret *al.* [34] report's value of 26.96 mg/kg. Numerous health benefits have been demonstrated by appropriate calcium intake, including a decrease in pregnancy-related hypertensive disorders, a decrease in blood pressure, especially in young people, a prevention of osteoporosis and colorectal adenomas, a reduction in cholesterol, and a reduction in blood pressure in the offspring of mothers who consume adequate calcium during pregnancy [35]. Despite this, calcium is necessary at every stage of life. Depending on the reference recommendations, dietary reference levels for people over 19 years ranges from 1000 mg to 1300 mg [36]. In 2010, the USA Institute of Medicine (IOM) established a dietary intake upper limit of 3000 mg/day for pregnant women between the ages of 14 and 18 and 2500 mg/day for older women. Although the WHO advises 1.5–2 g daily, there is some research that suggests less than 1 g daily would be adequate [37]. This suggests that the seeds can provide their users with a substantial amount of calcium.

The estimated magnesium content of the seeds was 64.0 mg/kg, which is less than the range of values (14,255.82 to 474.92 mg Kg⁻¹) reported by Kumar *et al.* [43] but greater than the range of values (2.68–4.40 mg/g) reported by Vinhaet *al.* [31]

Magnesium is crucial in preventing heart-related conditions such as cardiac arrests, strokes, and heart attacks. Additionally, it has been linked to a decrease in blood pressure [38]. According to studies conducted on rats, diets low in magnesium is linked to anomalies in the gut *microbiota*, which ultimately cause disturbances in the gut-brain axis and the emergence of depressive-like behaviors [39]. A magnesium tolerated upper intake level (UL) of 350 mg/day was set for adults by the US Institute of Medicine (IOM) Dietary Reference Intakes (DRI) Committee in 1997 [40]. According to Kumar *et al.* [51] there is a correlation between magnesium intake and the incidence of depression; a moderate intake of magnesium was protective, but a high or low intake raised the risk of depression. Additionally, they advise that the dietary requirements for magnesium be modified to account for varying age groups.

The seeds' potassium content was estimated to be 95.5 mgKg⁻¹ which is less than (33,874.68 to 8365.31 mgkg⁻¹) in both the fruit and leaves [41], although Adeoye *et al.* [10] reported (13.70 to 244.37 mg/100 g) range of values, which is less than the value reported in this report. Sodium was not detected in the seed sample, however, Kumar *et al.* [51] reports 0.04% and Adeoye *et al.* [10] report concentration range of 9.00 to 98.33 mg/100 g (ie 0.900 to 9.833 mgKg⁻¹). Healthy adults require higher dietary potassium intake [52]. Increasing dietary potassium intake in mice reduces the sensitivity of the distal nephron to the sodium-retaining hormone aldosterone [53]. In general population, there are claims that excessive restriction of sodium may not only have minimal benefits for lowering blood pressure, but may also increase blood cholesterol levels and the risk of mortality [54]. The daily sodium intake limit recommended by World Health Organization (WHO) and clinical practice guidelines is 2.0–2.4 g per day [55]. Potassium requirements undoubtedly vary with a number of factors including energy needs, race, and intake of sodium. The average potassium intake of US adults participating in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 2011-2012 was 2795±34 mg/day [56]. Furthermore, Park *et al.* [41] reports sodium-potassium intake ratio does not significantly associate with the risk of diabetes mellitus in either men or women. Although, the seed could make significant contribution as a source of potassium, it indicates the sodium should be obtained from other source available.

The examined seeds had an estimated zinc concentration of 13.5 mg/kg, which is lower than that of Park *et al.* [41] but greater than that of Akintunde *et al.* [60]. Because it is essential to many physiological functions, including cell growth and development, metabolism, cognitive function, immune system function, and reproduction, zinc is a multifunctional trace element for the human body [61]. Significant health hazards are linked to zinc shortage, whereas excessive zinc consumption can have negative effects that include symptoms such as anaemia, neutropenia, and zinc-induced copper deficiency [62]. Guidelines for dietary zinc intake have been issued by a number of organisations; the World Health Organisation (WHO) in 2023, states that the dietary reference value is between 6.7 and 15 mg daily. The Food and Drug Administration (FDA) permits 40 mg daily, while the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) sets the tolerated upper intake level (UL) at 25 mg [63]. The findings of this investigation are within the WHO's acceptable range.

The papaya seed's flavonoid concentration (6.98 g/100 g) is higher than the papaya extracts' (235–2070 mg GAE/100 g) reported by Jeon *et al.* [51]. Flavonoids do not have any Recommended Daily Allowances or Dietary Reference Intakes [64]. The National Health and Nutritional Examination Survey (NHANES) and other data indicate that the median daily consumption of total flavonoids in the United States is 250 mg [65]. According to Pokhrel and Karki [52], flavonoids' greatest quality is their ability to function as antioxidants, shielding the organism from reactive oxygen species and free radicals. The papaya seeds' high flavonoid concentration (6.98 g/100 g) may place them among the most intriguing classes of naturally occurring phenolic compounds [66].

The seeds' alkaloid concentration (1.85 g/100 g) is higher (1.07%) than that of Rahmasariet *et al.* [52] but lower (3.09%) than that of Devi *et al.* [52]. Alkaloids are effective in eliminating worms from the human alimentary canal because of their anti-protozoal and anti-amoebic properties. They also exhibit antioxidant action [67]. Alkaloids are hazardous to people even though they are useful in treating a variety of illnesses [68]. Consequently, the US Food and Drug Administration removed all pyrrolizidine alkaloids, including comfrey products, from the market, while the German Federal Department of Health restricted their usage to less than 1 µg per day for a maximum of 6 weeks. If the use was

extended, the daily limit should be lowered to 0.1 µg/day [69]. Hence, the seeds should be use with caution.

The papaya seeds had 3.12 mg of phytate per 100 g of the dried sample, which is less than the 6.54–9.25 mg/100 g reported by Oyeleke *et al.* [19]. With di- and trivalent metallic ions including Ca, Cd, Mg, Zn, and Fe, phytate can form chelates to create insoluble compounds that are difficult for the gastrointestinal tract to absorb, hence, lower their bioavailability. Since the concentration of phytate in the seed was less than 250 mg/100 g, there is no risk that it may decrease the elemental bioavailability [70].

The seed had a higher oxalate concentration (7.50 mg/100 g) than Oyeleke *et al.* [71] but lower oxalate content than Rahmasariet *al.* [26]. The seeds had less oxalate than safe for human ingestion, which is 250 mg/100 g [72]small levels of oxalate are typically found in a variety of fruits and vegetables, but they do not provide any nutritional issues [19]. However, the oxalate concentration of papaya seeds decreases with increasing ripening stage [61].

The seed's estimated hydrogen cyanide concentration was 0.25 mg/100 g. This estimate was lower than the 0.64 mg/100 g reported by Kolu et al. [20], but it was comparable (0.31 mg/100 g) to the study of Akintunde *et al.* [60]. It is possible that the seed's low cyanide content was caused by the drying process [73]. Cyanide can be efficiently removed by soaking and air drying at temperatures between 28 and 40 degrees Celsius since the hydrogen cyanide is soluble in water and volatile (at 25 degrees Celsius) [75]. The seeds' 0.25 mg/100 g cyanide concentration is less than the adult deadly oral cyanide dosage of 0.5 to 3.5 mg/kg body weight (Park *et al.*, 2024). The seeds are therefore safe to eat.

The papaya seed's tannin content (0.1195 mg/100 g) is lower than that of the unripe papaya seeds (84.12 mg/100 g) [60]. and the sun-dried and oven-dried *Carica papaya* seed samples (52.92 and 66.50 mg/100 g, respectively) [20], but lower than that of the Martial-Didier *et al.* [32] report. The variation could be as a result of the ripining status of the *Carica papaya* seeds [60].Tannin has been reported to be responsible for decrease in feed intake, growth rate, feed efficiency and protein digestibility in experimental animals [70]. Therefore, foods rich in

tannins are considered to be of low nutritional value [73]. They are known to bind irreversibly to proteins and form insoluble complexes with them and thus rendering them indigestible by intestinal enzymes thereby interfering with their bioavailability [68]. The toxic effects of tannin depend upon their chemical structure and dosage [73]. The condensed tannin content of the seeds in this research may not lead to toxicity since the total acceptable tannic acid daily intake for a human being is 560 mg/100 g and further reduced during traditional processing [74].

The estimated amount of steroid in the seeds was 1.08 mg/100 g; however, neither Agada *et al.* [74] nor Kolu et al. [20] found any steroid in the aqueous extracts of *carica papaya seeds*. One of the key secondary metabolites that have essential functions in animals as *immune stimulants and hypocholesterolaemic agents* is steroids. They are used to lower blood cholesterol levels, improve animal body weight growth and feed efficiency, raise intestinal mucosal cell permeability in vitro, block active mucosal transport, and make it easier for compounds that are often not absorbed to be absorbed [75]. According to some research, there are more hazards associated with steroids than advantages [75].

4.0 Conclusion

The analysis of the *carica papaya* seeds revealed that they were nutritious and that their anti-nutrient levels were within permissible bounds; however, the concentration of alkaloids suggested that the seeds should be used with caution.

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